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BluLeaf®: a Decision Support System (DSS) for agricultural water management

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Abstract

Agriculture 4.0 is transforming farming by integrating digital technologies in cultivation practices in order to boost production, optimize the usage of resources, and enhance sustainability. In this context, water management plays a crucial role, especially in the Mediterranean region, where the scarcity of water, variability in climatic conditions, and soil degradation pose significant obstacles to crop production. Water management represents a particularly challenging topic as excessive (or insufficient) irrigation can cause damage such as reduce the quality or the quantity of the yield. An efficient water management is even more important, if considering the increasing global food production demands and the impacts of climate change. Decision Support Systems (DSSs) are digital tools for modern agriculture, capable of helping farmers to improve their cultivation practices. DSSs are designed to collect, process, and provide relevant information, even the complex one, with simplicity and immediacy. DSSs take advantage of advanced technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT) and Cloud Computing, to implement telemetry and control features and to execute data processing algorithms to generate summarizing indicators and powerful insights. This paper offers a comprehensive introduction to the BluLeaf® platform for digital agriculture, a cloud-based solution integrating a DSS specifically designed for agricultural water management. BluLeaf® employs real-time data coming from IoT devices and agronomical models to optimize irrigation schedules based on specific crop needs, promoting awareness in agricultural practices. BluLeaf® is served to users as a web-based application as well as a mobile application for Android and iOS devices.

Key words: digital agriculture, decision support system, irrigation management, cloud computing, agronomical models